

“Need And Importance Of Translation Of Indian Languages Vice Versa To Promote Indian Educational Scenario”

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ABSTRACT

Today, we are living in a global world, where linguistic communication in several languages is used as a channel or interaction in between boundaries, to meet our fundamental needs. All of the above is feasible because of the process of linguistic translation. The translation is the natural extension of any verbal communication we desire to express and spans four bridges: personal, linguistic, cultural, and commercial. All cognitive ideas exchanged from antiquity to the present rely on individuals who can shift words from one language to another in order to create sentences, thoughts, feelings, and desired themes. India is an ethnically and linguistically diverse country that acknowledges and treats with respect many practices, like cultures, traditions, and languages. Linguistic variety is extensive and distinct in every region of the nation. There are five language groups in India, 14 main writing systems, 400 spoken languages, and thousands of dialects. Throughout India's history, translation has served to bind the country together. Without translation's purpose, ideas and notions such as "Indian literature," "Indian culture," "Indian philosophy," and "Indian knowledge systems" would not have been feasible. Translation is critical in a multilingual society like India, where a new language is introduced every 25 kilometres, and translation in multiple languages encourages the national integration of the country's numerous regional cultures. Linguistic translation creates multilingual knowledge with different linguistic cultures and literature, and national cohesion may be achieved by developing a shared social vision. The translation is also required for our country's emotional liberation and well-being. This paper described the scope, need, importance, and procedures for translation in Indian languages and vice versa, with special reference to the conference theme "Translating Across Languages, Cultures, & Disciplines". We have framed questions for data collection related to the scope and procedures of language translation, its popularity, and futuristic trends, and collected online responses from the concerned respondents. We used descriptive techniques for our study, using a random selection sampling method. The data was collected from a variety of primary and secondary sources, including websites, magazines, journals, Google Forms, and expert comments. The questionnaire (Google Form) was used to capture data, which was then analyzed with diagrams.

Keywords: translation, Indian languages, communication, multilingualism, accuracy,

1. Introduction

We always want the translation to be a bridge between first and second languages that represents locations, territories, nations, states, regions, societies, religions, or countries. We are trying to change one word for another, but a translation can help us learn more about socioeconomic issues and native cultures by bringing ideas across regional, linguistic, and national borders. Translation represents examples of how it has helped rich, indigenous cultures pass from one nation to another, such as India. We learn two languages at a time with novel concepts and ideas, and we understand each other better. This has made it feasible for language proficiency to be employed and encouraged through learning and collaborating toward legally binding security in the respective language. The process of translation is more than just an exercise in interlanguage communication. It is more complicated than

just substituting text written in the source language with content written in the target language, and it incorporates cultural and educational subtleties that have the potential to impact the choices and attitudes of receivers.

2. Need and Importance of Bilingual Translation

India has 22 official languages in its constitution under Schedule 8. According to the Census Report 2011, more than 19,500 languages or dialects are spoken as mother tongues in India, according to the latest analysis of a census conducted in 2011 and published in 2018. However, 96.71 percent of the population speaks one of the 22 official languages as their mother tongue, and 121 languages are spoken by 10,000 or more people in India separately, which has a population of 121 billion, according to a report, but till date we have been unable to choose a single national language for our motherland as a mother tongue India. India has no official national language to date, but the Indian constitution states that "the official language of the Union shall be Hindi in Devanagari script" in article 343(1). The international version of Indian numerals should be utilized for official Union activities." The "Continuation of English Language for Official Purposes of the Union and for Use in Parliament" in Clause 3 of the Official Languages Act, 1963, makes English and Hindi the Official Languages of the Union Government of India, along with 22 other official languages called state languages of India. These days, every second person in India is connected to the internet. They are using English as the most popular foreign language according to the three language formulae, but as their first language, they have chosen from 19500 languages, beside 22 constitutional languages, which creates a great need to coordinate the local language(Mother tongue) with English or would be national language, This creates a greater need to translate information written in one regional language to another, If we want to attract more people and win their loyalty towards the motherland, we need to find a way to communicate with them in their known language, which creates a translational need in India.

Origin of Indian Languages

3. India Needs Translation

India is a fast-growing economy in the world, India has a need for translation that has expanded and advanced in education, tourism, religion, commerce, business, science, and technology. Despite Hindi and Urdu being widely used in India, many individuals don't recognize them, development and growth need to connect with your audience in their own language. Translation expands reach and connections to the target audience, if you work in Tamil Nadu, Tamil will help you stand out, you would reach and attract more people with a translation of the concerned language. The demand for translation in India is increasing due to a growing desire among individuals to access education in their mother tongue. Global and local institutions have modified their content strategies to incorporate regional content, resulting in a demand for multilingual content and, consequently, an increase in trends in translation in India. Translation has proven to be highly advantageous not only for national and local institutions such as education, tourism, religion, commerce, business, science, technology, film, music, and tourism, among others. Currently, the production of translated and subtitled films has become a significant source of revenue. In addition, the act of translating content, films, songs, literature, and other forms of literature enables writers and creators to expand their reach and enhance their level of recognition among audiences at the local, national, and international levels.

3.1 The Translator

The translator plays a crucial role in interpreting the original source and ideas around cultural and linguistic barriers, which puts a translator in an especially key position to comprehend a variety of modern concepts and understand different linguistic cultures and the meaning of the new words. Many countries are greatly aided by translating tales from around the globe, and India is one of them, which serves as a priceless source of information

about different aspects of languages, indigenous cultures, and experiences. Additionally, translation may play a significant role in cultural transmission, the creation of values, defining politics, and serving as a catalyst for rapprochement or social integration. Therefore, the way that worldwide issues related to human rights are expressed and transmitted may be significantly altered by translations.

3.2 Translation by Machine

Language translation by machine is better than translation by a human translator or manual translation because machine translation is faster and less expensive. Online, with websites, artificial intelligence, or with Artificial Intelligence or with computer, language translation can be performed very easily right away, and it costs less than of what it used to. Even though machine translation (MT) is getting better and better, most educational and translational experts think that it can't replace manual translation. Many educational fields, institutions, and service providers choose to combine their translation processes in two ways: first, by using machine translation (MT), followed by doing some editing by a human manual translator to improve the quality and accuracy of the contents and their real meaning and originality. When the two way process has been completed, machine translation can speed up the process of translation without lowering the quality of the final product. In addition to its usage for personal purposes, machine translation (MT) assists translational fields with expanding their reach to vast audiences all over the world. The content of websites are being translated into an increasing number of languages in order to assist break down barriers caused by a linguistic hurdle. When you see translation in today's scenario, the words are in an unknown language you are unfamiliar with, but you can now use a machine translation or online tool to find out what they mean in your known language instantly. Basically, this is the process of machine translation that is "a way for a computer to change an unknown language into a known language."

3.3 Literary Translation

Many institutes worldwide translate literature. Translating international as well as Indian literature and vice versa is profitable. Sahitya Akademi, the National Book Trust, regional literary groups, and language publishing businesses are profitable businesses. Young non resident Indians who do not speak their languages are eager to read their literature in translation in the languages they know, while foreign readers are curious about Indian literature. Recent literary festivals, book fairs, and others have contributed to this growing interest. The government of India launched Indian Literature Abroad (ILA) to address this increased interest. Penguin, Macmillan, Orient Longman, Oxford University Press, Harper-Collins, Hatchett, and other Indian publishing firms are actively promoting literary and discursive translations.

4. Urdu and English Translation vice versa

English is of Germanic origin and was initially spoken in England during the Middle Ages. Although Latin is the most common alphabet used for writing English, other scripts exist for the language as well. The alphabet consists of 26 different symbols, including upper- and lower-case versions of each. The direction of writing in English is left-to-right. Urdu is a Persian record of Hindustani called Urdu, often known as Lashkar. It is one of the constitutional languages of India. Naskh and Taliq script, a hybrid of Persian and Arabic, are used to write Urdu. The "Tahajji" alphabet of Urdu consists of 39 letters and is written from right to left.

4.1 Procedure of Translation vice versa

The practice of making literary works into written form through translation from English to Urdu or any Indian language or vice versa is a very difficult task, and it has been in existence since the inception of written literature. Humanistic and machine translation is a branch of intelligence and artificial intelligence that involves the use of a human brain, a computer, or other machine equipped with a dictionary in both languages and vice versa; it is called a program, and directions are given to make logical decisions and choices. Its primary objective is to translate textual words into natural language, including sentences, phrases, and words. The field of translation incorporates concepts from various interdisciplinary domains, including linguistics, computer science, artificial intelligence, statistics, and mathematics. The translated text's structural mystery is rooted in the source language, while the translated language serves as the target language for the translation. The translation process ensures the preservation of the taste and perception of the text input while also maintaining the intended purpose and melody of the information throughout the sentence. In this paper, we are discussing these procedures of translation as a research study and trying to find out the scope, need, and importance of translation for the betterment of Indian educational scenarios that can be enhanced with linguistic translation.

5. Review of Related Studies

According to Dingwaney (1995), translations are unavoidably impacted by cultural and political factors and cannot be separated from the surrounding context of the original texts. This means the translation is very important work for culture, national building, and understanding one's information. In David Katan (2004) perspective in his work "Translating Cultures," every language translator serves as an intermediary agent who is bilingual and facilitates dialogue among those who are monolingual and belong to two distinct language communities (Katan, 2004). Translators are required to act as intermediaries between distinct language systems and as intercultural

mediators. As per Aniela Korzeniowska statement in their work titled Successful Polish-English Translation Tricks of the Trade (2006), translators must possess the qualities of being 'bilingual and bicultural'. Translation plays a pivotal role in comprehending cultural differences. When we find a new language, we need to understand and search for new literature that will help us to determine the culture and civilization of the said community, and we also try to introduce our own culture and coordinate them accordingly. In this particular case of the recently found languages, an indigenous language that researchers came across while studying Aka and Miji. They have discovered new, widely accepted languages in India. It creates an example of how translation enhances knowledge and information about a new culture and civilization in our national cultures. The 'Enduring Voices' initiative of National Geographic led to the discovery of the said language (Morrison 2010). The newly identified dialect set itself apart from the more well-known ones in terms of words, sentences, sounds, and the organizational structure of the grammar, according to the linguistic experts. The distinctions in alphabetical order and with sound between two languages may be likened to those between English and Urdu/Hindi. Linguistic experts are concerned about this vulnerable language, which is only spoken by around a thousand individuals, in part, but has no written form. This essential component could also seem to be one of the biggest challenges a translator would encounter.

6. Research Methodology

This article, “**Need and Importance of Translation of Indian Languages Vice Versa to Promote Indian Educational Scenario,**” discusses the translational need, importance, opportunities, and impact on Indian educational development, especially after NEP-2020, where primary education should be provided in the mother tongue. In 1950, languages and dialects represented India in the educational field. To discuss translational studies and their impact, we framed questions for data collection related to the translation of Indian languages and vice versa, its uses, popularity, futuristic scopes, and trends. For this purpose, we collected online responses from the concerned respondents and prepared tables and graphs for the results and analysis. We have used descriptive techniques for our study; the total sample was 130 ($N = 130$), and we used a random selection method and collected information from both first-hand and second-hand sources.

6.1 Questions Framed for Research

This study will try to find answers to a few research questions, such as:

- How does translation change the way people in India think about ancient literature?
- What are the futuristic trends in the translation of Indian languages into English?
- What are the benefits of translation for the Indian educational scenario?

6.2 Research objectives

In light of the aforementioned research questions, this paper aims to accomplish the following objectives:

- To know the importance of Indian literature to Indian culture and civilization.
- To evaluate the futuristic trends of translation in India.
- To know the impact of translation of Indian languages and vice versa for the upliftment of education.

6.3 Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data was collected from a variety of primary and secondary sources, including websites, magazines, journals, Google Forms, and interviews with educational experts. The questionnaire (a Google Form) was used to capture data, which was then analyzed with diagrams.

7. Question Framed for Data Collection

Table :01 Questions framed for data collection

Questions framed for Data Collections	Answers				Total Respondents
	Yes	No	May be	Not Sure	
Q. No.01. Do we need a foreign language in education?					
Q. No.02. Indian language translations into English are crucial for expanding access to education in the country?					
Q. No.03. Can translation be used to promote all Indian languages and literature in education?					
Q. No.04. Is the translation of Indian literature into other languages beneficial for Indian culture and civilization?					
Q. No.05. Can mother tongues of Indian origin be promoted through translation?					
Q. No.06. Can translation unite the Indian educational scenario?					

8. Analysis & Discussion of Results

8.1. Interpretation: A total of 130 respondents out of 130 (100%) participated in the said survey, and 68 respondents (52.3%) said that we need a foreign language (English) in the Indian educational system because "English is a window to the world" and it enhances educational practices and benefits the mother languages of the country, whereas just 26 respondents (20.2%) held this view. 30 out of 130 people surveyed said that either English or any mother tongue is the most up-to-date medium of instruction in education. They think that in the age of globalization, we need a global language, and it is not other than English, and English is an unofficial official language of India; therefore, we need English as one of the languages in the Indian educational scenario.

Figure: 8.1 Table of respondents, Srl.No.01 and its analysis with diagrams

8.2 Interpretation: A total of 129 respondents out of 130 (99.23%) participated in the said survey, and 98 (75.94%) of the respondents said that the features of translations of local languages into English are crucial for expanding access to education in the country and that it is suitable for young minds to coordinate between both languages. 13.17% said that translations of local languages into English create a cultural gap in Indian societies and are harmful for learners; 9.32% said that it focuses on a specific topic, so it may be beneficial for learners or may have an adverse impact on them; only 1.55% said that the translation is not original and is not goal-oriented, so they are unable to say something about translating Urdu to English or vice versa.

Figure: 8.2 Table of respondents, Srl.No.02 and its analysis with diagrams

8.3 Interpretation: A total of 127 respondents out of 130 (99.3%) participated in the said survey, and 87 (52.3%) of the respondents said that "translation should be used to promote all Indian languages and literature in education, and it is beneficial for Indian languages and literature that multi- or bi-lingual medium of instruction

is suitable for classroom teachings in India." They said that this trend follows the maxims and principles of teaching and learning, while only 8 respondents said that translation could not be an alternative to traditional single language-based teachings. 23.07% of respondents said that translation may be beneficial in the future because the two methods are the same. Only 4.61% of respondents were not sure.

Figure: 8.3 Table of respondents, Srl.No.03 and its analysis with diagrams

8.4 Interpretation: 97 respondents out of 124 (94.56%) of the people who answered said that translation of Indian language and literature into other languages is beneficial to transfer Indian culture and civilization vice versa, and they would use it in their classroom learning because they are confident enough that translational information will improve the quality of teaching and learning. Only 04.03% disagreed that translation of different languages will transfer values of Indian culture and civilization vice versa through literature. 12.09% of respondents thought that it is very difficult to improve the quality of education through language translation. It may be good, but they are not sure. On the other hand, 5.64% of respondents were not sure that translation format would be used in their teaching-learning process.

Figure: 8.4 Table of respondents, Srl.No.04 and its analysis with diagrams

8.5 Interpretation: 77.61% of respondents fixed their positive response on the fact that mother tongues of Indian origin will be promoted through translation and vice versa; they were sure that translation will improve language quality and standards, have a positive impact on the mother tongue, and improve the Indian education system as well. 15.09% of the respondents who took the survey did not agree that translation can improve the quality of education. They further express their views that translation cannot positively impact knowledge transfer from one person to another due to typical learning concepts in India. On the other hand, 10.37% of respondents

don't know if using this method will help students or change the concept of learning in India. 01.88% of respondents were not familiar with translational studies or what they would do.

Figure: 8.5 Table of respondents, Srl.No.05 and its analysis with diagrams

8.6 Interpretations: 32.55% of people agree that translation of Indian languages and vice versa can unite the Indian educational scenario into one India one unit, as Indian educational systems successfully follow three-language formulae everywhere in India. 16.29% of respondents do not agree that only translation can unite all Indian languages. 50.38% of respondents thought that translation can unite the Indian educational scenario with multilingual languages, but only translation can do this huge task, and it is a good addition to Indian education. Only 1.55% of respondents were not sure.

Figure: 8.6 Table of respondents, Srl.No.06 and its analysis with diagrams

8.7 Over all Result

We find some solutions with the said survey about the need **and importance of translation of Indian languages vice versa to promote the Indian educational scenario**; that is the need of the hour, and we find that translation will improve Indian culture and civilization with the translation of Indian languages vice versa and with English as well. It will be a futuristic trend and one of the demands and choices of the young learners, as according to the policy NEP-2020, the medium of instruction will be the mother tongue at the primary level. So here we can say that with the development of science and digital technology, new ways of translating are available. We may translate bulk literature accordingly, and we may edit it manually with reviews. We can create a vast Indian literature that will have a great impact on the Indian educational scenario. Now we can say that translation and multilingual mediums of instruction are a set of innovative, constantly changing learning

difficulties that schools all over India will start to use to keep up with the new translation trends and preferences of vast cultures and civilizations.

Figure: 8.7 Combined table and representation with diagram of the research analysis

9. Findings of the Study

The communication of research findings is a complicated process, similar to linguistic translation from one language to another. It is not just a question of how researchers represent their findings and in what form, by what means, and in what context, but the concept should be clear. Research findings always draw the attention of policymakers, and futuristic trends of the work have to be done, but some argue the real findings of the said study, and we did not do anything because we did not know what they were thinking, what their philosophical beliefs were, how far they sought to understand... Even if we want to assert that translation is feasible, practical, and beneficial from one language to another, we have to admit that there are significant challenges and hazards that may develop just as there are with language translation.

- We have seen similarities in translating texts from one language to another, conveying this finding, and drawing attention to policymakers and language translators.
- There have been several arguments about the difficulty of translating scientific terminology, typical words, and technical words from one language to another in general. This may be taken for review by the concerned subject experts.
- Problems might develop at the level of employing the grammar-specific vocabulary of a particular language; this could need to be flexible and simplified, as well as framed in shorter sentences. The structure and length of sentences will also often need to be adapted properly.
- There's also the question of who should do the actual job of translating and assessing the content of a language text; some people claim that translators should only translate into their mother tongue.
- It is acknowledged that much may be gained via translation, but there can also be losses.

Re-contextualizing ideas may be instructive and productive for education, culture and creation of one feeling to the nation.

- translation is a difficult process that requires profound knowledge of the languages of the translator or machine translation involved, but a reviewer must exercise deliberate judgment in order to attempt to make a translation that should be faithful to the original while at the same time being comprehensible to the audience that will be reading it.

10. Educational implications

When considering translation as an illustration of the interaction between studies and decisions or practices, there are two aspects that need to be looked at in isolation from one another. First, there is the process of disseminating the results of research to non-specialist audiences, and second, there is the procedure of applying the findings of research in real-world settings. I will go over each of them in turn.

- It is recommended that care and attention be paid to the translation, as it is vital. A good translation will always carefully take care of the words, culture, and phrases of one to another languages. Paying attention to the translation is essential.
- In addition to having strong communication abilities, a skilled translator should be familiar with the primary goals of a translation. These goals may include an audience, the sort of content being translated (for example, literary or technical), the aim of the translation (for example, to enlighten or inspire), and so on. The translator will be able to carry out their duties effectively in this manner.
- The ability to communicate efficiently with both languages and vice versa is essential to the development of high-quality translation work. Translation is a two-way street, and that means that both the translator and the audience of both languages need to be actively involved in the process of sharing ideas.
- **Accuracy:** A translation must express the same meaning as the source text and accurately represent the original author's intended meaning in order to be considered accurate.
- **Clarity:** in the context of translation, is making sure a text is easily understood. Once again, this is a complicated yet nebulous concept. For a translation to be accurate, the source and target texts must be written in such a way that there is no confusion between them.
- **Authenticity:** A language translation should not seem to be a translation in another language in any way, including how it sounds, reads, or looks. This is one of the most basic principles of translation. Therefore, authenticity is an essential component of any translation that is of high quality, it must be maintained accordingly. Languages, much like living beings, are in a constant state of flux and development. Every facet of their language, including its spelling, grammar, and vocabulary, is evolving. As a result, a competent translator will make every effort to keep current with the languages, keeping in mind that accuracy, clarity, authenticity, the appropriate manner and temperament, cultural appropriateness, consistency, and the language of the present day are the essential parts to take care of when we translate linguistic literature and vice versa.

11. Conclusion:

The process of language translation and vice versa poses a significant challenge, primarily due to the absence of high-quality text and the grammatical complexity inherent in Indian languages. In order to enhance the quality of translations by a humanistic translator or neural machine translation (NMT) system, it is essential that the text dimensions be substantial, and it is compulsory to break the big sentences into parts that create a simple understanding for the audience. Furthermore, it is important that the parallel sentences exhibit comparable semantic content while also addressing distinct domains. Utilizing a collection of texts to represent the real concept of the condensed text can provide a reliable means of evaluating the efficacy of translations. The present language translation and vice versa constitute translators' contributions to the research community in the field of linguistic translation. The English and Indian languages exhibit contrasting levels of morphological complexity. To enhance the quality of translation, it may be beneficial to incorporate linguistic attributes into the sentences. Translation may have a variety of purposes, including that of a "unifier" or the creation of new terms, but perhaps its most important function is that of an informational resource on other cultures that are less well known. Therefore, translation is not just a language activity; it also has the potential to have an effect on politics and society.

References

1. Amilia, Ika & Yuwono, Darmawan. (2020). A STUDY OF THE TRANSLATION OF GOOGLE TRANSLATE. LINGUA : JURNAL ILMIAH. 16. 1-21. 10.35962/lingua.v16i2.50. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347009752_A_STUDY_OF_THE_TRANSLATION_OF_GOOGLE_TRANSLATE
2. Andrabi, Syed & Wahid, Abdul. (2022). Machine Translation System Using Deep Learning for English to Urdu. Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience. 2022. 1-11. 10.1155/2022/7873012. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357548737_Machine_Translation_System_Using_Deep_Learning_for_English_to_Urdu
3. B. King and S. Abney, "Labelling the languages of words in mixed-language documents using weakly supervised methods," in *Proc. North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, Atlanta, Georgia, USA, pp. 1110–1119, 2013.
4. Bakshi, Gursimran Kaur. (2021), official languages of India : a descriptive analysis" available at <https://blog.ipleaders.in/official-languages-india-descriptive-analysis/>
5. Bernacka, A (2012) 'The Importance of Translation Studies for Development Education', Policy and Practice: A Development Education Review, Vol. 14, Spring, pp. 113-118. Available at The Importance of Translation Studies for Development Education | Development Education Review
6. Budick, S and Iser, W (1996) *The Translatability of Cultures*, Stanford, California: Stanford University Press.
7. Dingwaney, A (1995) 'Introduction: Translating "Third World" Cultures' in A Dingwaney and C Maier (eds.) *Between Languages and Cultures*, London: University of Pittsburgh Press.

8. H. Choudhary, A. K. Pathak, R. R. Shah and P. Kumaraguru, "Neural machine translation for English-Tamil," in *Proc. Conf. on Machine Translation*, Belgium, Brussels, pp. 770–775, 201
9. Hotz Lee, R (2010) 'Rare Find: A New Language' in *Environment and Science*, available: <http://online.wsj.com/article/SB10001424052748703843804575534122591921594.html>.
10. Rauf, S. (2020, May 16). *On the Exploration of English to Urdu Machine Translation.*, European Language Resources Association (ELRA), licensed under CC-BY-NC, available at <https://aclanthology.org/2020.sltu-1.40.pdf>.
11. <https://www.milestoneloc.com/top-qualities-of-a-good-translation/#:~:text=The%20top%20qualities%20of%20a%20good%20translator%20are%20being%20able,of%20what%20is%20being%20said>.
12. I. Mathur, N. Joshi, H. Darbari and A. Kumar, "Automatic evaluation of ontology matchers," I n *Proc. Int. Conf. on Transport Science*, Udaipur, India, pp. 1–6, 2016.
13. N. Joshi, I. Mathur and S. Mathur, "Translation memory for Indian languages: An aid for hum an translators," in *Proc. Int. Conf. & Workshop on Emerging Trends in Technology*, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India, pp. 711–714, 2011.
14. P. Dubey, "Natural language processing," *JK Knowledge Initiative*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 89–91, 2 017.
15. S. H. Kumhar, S. I. Ansarullah, A. A. Gardezi, S. Ahmad, A. E. Sayed *et al.*, "Translation of english language into urdu language using lstm model," *Computers, Materials & Continua*, vol.74, no.2, pp. 3899–3912, 2023 available at <https://techscience.com/cmc/v74n2/50241/html>
16. S. H. Kumhar, W. Qadir, M. M. Kirmani, H. Bashir and M. Hassan, 2021, "Effectiveness of m ethods and tools used for collection of roman Urdu and English multilingual corpus," *Design Engineering*, vol. 2021, no. 7, pp. 13428–13438, pp. 2021.
17. V. Goyal and G. S. Lehal, "Advances in machine translation systems," *Languages in India*, vo l. 9, no. 11, pp. 139–150, 2009.
18. **Meghna Paul** (2021) Blog Language Curry, "Understanding the needs of translation in India"Availbale at: <https://blogs.languagecurry.com/articles/understanding-the-importance-of-translation-in-india>
19. 19. *PTI (2018)* "More than 19,500 mother tongues spoken in India: Census 2011" *The Times pf India*, New Delhi | July 1, 2018 14:13 IST Available at <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/more-than-19500-mother-tongues-spoken-in-india-census-5241056/>